

Read-me

This dataset was part of the PhD work of Bessibié Bazongo from Institute of Rural Development, Nazi BONI University, 01 BP 1091 Bobo-Dioulasso, Burkina Faso. The work was carried out in 2021 and 2022 and focused on “**Influence of Shrub Proximity, Species, and Management on Sorghum Productivity and Soil Biology in Low-Input Sudanian Agroforestry Systems.**”

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Related article: A paper was recently submitted to the journal *Agroforestry Systems*

Presentation of the field work:

The study was carried out in the northern Sudanian zone of Burkina Faso, in the villages of Nassoulou, Nandiala, Saria and Poa-Yaoguin. It investigated the impact of common agroforestry systems found in central-west Burkina Faso on four key sustainability indicators: sorghum yield, soil labile carbon, soil macrofauna density and their ecological indices. Our research was designed to determine how shrub proximity, species, and management influence these indicators.

A two-year study (2021-2022) was conducted on 252 sorghum plots across a 300 km² area to compare five management strategies. The plots were classified as a control group with no adjacent trees (T0), or were managed by either pruning *P. reticulatum* (T1) or pruning *G. senegalensis* (T2), by allowing *P. reticulatum* to regenerate naturally (T3), or by mulching the soil with tree residues (T4). Sorghum yield and soil labile carbon were measured in all plots, while soil macrofauna characteristics were quantified in a random subset.

Description of the data base:

It consists in an excel file with three sheets:

The sheet named database indicate in successive columns the values collected for each indicator per village (Nassoulou, Nandiala, Saria and Poa-Yaoguin), treatment (T0 to T4) and year (2021 and 2022).

DM means that the data is missing.

The sheet named Stats1, Tables+ indicated the results of the statistical analysis with R.

The sheet named Scripts report the code used in R to compare the correlations between the measured indicators.